

THE IMPORTANCE OF CLIL IN ESP TEACHING

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Abstract. This article highlights the importance of integrating CLIL and ESP approaches in teaching the students who learn a specific field. In this paper the author researches some of the ideas given for the combination of these two approaches. Besides the writer suggests and describes a strategy which can be a good use of integrating CLIL and ESP. In the conclusion the author finishes with own proposals.

Key words: CLIL, ESP, English for specific purposes, integration, approach.

Introduction. Nowadays Uzbekistan is integrating to big global organisations, and this requires reformation in all the spheres. In its turn it means our students cannot learn only the language itself, but also must get some special knowledge in their sphere. That's why to my view integrating ESP and CLIL is an important issue at present.

Before starting my article, let me define the terms ESP and CLIL. Describing the term ESP as English for specific purposes “refers to teaching the special vocabulary in English to people who are preparing themselves to work in various professional fields”. Deciphering CLIL as “content and language integrated learning is an approach for learning a special content by using language skills in which both the subject and the language are taught”. ESP is focused only on the language

mastering, whereas in CLIL students learn not only the language itself, but also get knowledge in the target professional field. Considering above we can conclude that integration of those two aspects create a real-world in which students will have the opportunity to master the skills they will need in their future employment. However, most of our present textbooks are based on traditional methods of teaching such as memorizing the words and using them in the exercises.

Till now several advantages have been proposed by many scholars. Coyle says that CLIL increases “learner’s linguistic competence and confidence”. Dudley-Evans refers to CLIL as subject language integration in which both language and content are educated by the linguist teacher. Besides, merge of these two aspects will “provide the students with sufficient language skills to develop content knowledge’. In ESP students are considered to be the experts in a specific area of work, while the teacher is the expert in the target language. While learning students can use, apart from the target language, their mother tongue as well as other languages. In a result teachers are engaged in designing pedagogical materials and in-class activities and thus meeting the needs of the learners in a special discipline and context.

In a theory, ESP and CLIL have some similar key features:

- ~ both use the context in different non-linguistic subjects;
- ~ both use communicational methodology in language teaching;
- ~ both develop academic and communicative skills.

However, ESP and CLIL have also contrasting points:

- ~ approaches are different to the target language;
- ~ objectives and learning outcomes are different;
- ~ teacher’s role is different.

Overall, we conclude that ESP can be taught by a linguist teacher, but CLIL can be delivered any teacher who is specialized in the content sphere and have command of the language. Krupchenko & Kuznetsov claim that collaboration

between area-specific specialist and a language teacher will be just be an exact answer to integrate CLIL and ESP. For instance, this collaboration may be conducted by co-teaching.

However, there are some key features to be considered while integrating these two aspects: CLIL and ESP. In ESP there is a goal and all the materials should be adapted to the learners' level, whilst in CLIL the target language serves as a means for learning. This means there are strategies to be used. One strategy which can bridge CLIL and ESP is scaffolding.

- ~ Firstly, the fundamental knowledge is activated;
- ~ then the tasks are divided into small easy parts;
- ~ after some expressions, idioms, phrases to be used;
- ~ next the context is given for information;
- ~ lastly terms and terminology will be taught.

During the process the teacher can use visual aids and mnemonic devices to ease the learning process.

Having analysed the above ideas we can conclude that combination of these two approaches is used at universities or for learners who are preparing themselves for employment. This means that while tailoring the tasks or activities the teacher should consider the needs and the language level of the learners.

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